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Comparative Analysis of the Heat Retention Capabilities of Cow fat and Shea Butter as Potential Phase Change Materials

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ABSTRACT

More Phase change materials are being investigated to find a more affordable, available and nontoxic alternatives to the currently used ones. Cow fat and Shea butter due to their availability and affordability in the Northern part of Nigeria could serve as better PCM options for people in the area. In this study Shea butter and cow fat materials are investigated for their suitability as phase change materials. To do this, two identical grade cookers with provisions for the inclusion of phase change materials were used. One (1) liter each of the PCMs materials was weighed and used for the study. The two quantities were poured into the identical cookers labelled Shea butter cooker and cow Fat cooker kept overnight so that they both stabilized at the same temperatures. They were then taken to the testing ground and exposed to direct sunlight to conduct boiling tests using distilled water. The temperatures of the water were recorded at regular intervals until the water boiled. The two cookers were then simultaneously taken into a room so that the waters in the chambers can gradually lose heat. The results showed that the water on cow fat cooker attained boiling point faster in 39 minutes than the one on Shea butter cooker in 42 minutes and that the absorber plate temperatures rose as high as 133 °C and 136 °C for shea butter and cow fat cooker with second figure of merit F2 0.48 and 0.50 respectively. On the other hand, although Shea cooker took longer time to attain boiling point it however took longer period to lose heat. Seven (7) hours after taking the cookers away from the sun, the temperature of water in the Shea butter cooker was 55.7 °C and that of cow Fat-cooker was 42.3 °C. This results show that both materials have a good potential to be harnessed as heat storage.

Keywords: PCMs, cow fat, shea butter, boiling test, stagnation test, solar cookers

INTRODUCTION

Solar cooking offers a simple, safe, and fuel-free method of food preparation without contributing to indoor heat or environmental pollution (Buddhi et al., 1999). The integration of thermal energy storage (TES) into solar cooking units has emerged as a promising approach to extend cooking beyond sunshine hours and maintain food at desirable temperatures. TES enhances system efficiency by reducing heat

losses, improving heat transfer, and enabling energy storage for later use (Schwarzer et al., 2003; Saxena et al., 2020). Phase Change Materials (PCMs) are particularly attractive in this regard because they can store large amounts of latent heat at nearly constant temperatures, allowing for efficient energy charging and discharging cycles (Javadi et al., 2020).

Several researchers have demonstrated the benefits of incorporating PCMs in solar cookers. Omara et al. (2020) reported that PCM integration could improve overall utilization efficiency by up to 85% while reducing heating time by 15%. Evacuated tube-based systems, coupled with heat transfer fluids (HTFs), have also been explored for their ability to minimize heat losses and rapidly transfer energy to PCM-based cooking units (Hebbar et al., 2021; Chaudhary et al., 2020). Concentrating solar cookers, though less common, have achieved higher cooking temperatures, with reported oven temperatures up to 175 °C (Reddy et al., 2009; Suharat et al., 2000).

TES methods are generally categorized as sensible heat storage, latent heat storage, or thermochemical storage. Among these, latent heat storage using PCMs is the most effective due to high energy density and near-isothermal behavior during phase transitions (Sharma et al., 2009; Glatzmaier et al., 2013). However, the low thermal conductivity of many PCMs remains a challenge, limiting heat transfer rates and cooking power density. Researchers have therefore investigated different PCM types and configurations to overcome these issues. Buddhi et al. (1997) used stearic acid, while Domanski et al. (1995) and Sharma et al. (2000, 2005) explored magnesium nitrate hexahydrate and erythritol for box-type and evacuated tube solar cookers. Results confirmed that evening cooking could be achieved, although cooking times were sometimes extended due to slow discharge rates (Zhao et al., 2018).

Hybrid systems combining collectors, reflectors, and PCM storage units have also been reported. Hussein et al. (2013) designed an indirect solar cooker with flat-plate collectors, reflectors, and PCM storage, achieving a 24% daily performance improvement. Munir et al. (2010) and Kenisarin et al. (2007) used advanced PCMs such as A-164, capable of maintaining hot plate temperatures around 140–150 °C, suitable for frying. Other studies (Nkhonjera et al., 2017; Regattieri et al., 2016) emphasized the humanitarian applications of TES-based concentrator cookers, particularly for off-grid regions.

Indoor and indirect cooking systems have been studied to allow cooking away from direct sunlight. Heat pipe-based collectors demonstrated efficiencies twice that of steam cookers without requiring tracking (Khalifa et al., 2011). Ramadan et al. (2007) and Agrawal et al. (2015) used sensible heat storage materials such as sand, stone pebbles, and iron grits, while Yadav et al. (2013) combined latent (acetamide) and sensible (sand) storage units for dual cooking, reporting evening cooking up to two times faster than noon cooking. Similarly, Sreepathi et al. (2017) and Veremachi et al. (2016) demonstrated PCM storage units with oxalic acid and nitrate mixtures, reaching suitable cooking and frying temperatures. Advanced designs such as the “Sun Bucket” achieved PCM melting temperatures of up to 334 °C, enabling a wide range of cooking applications (Floess, 2019; Tesfay et al., 2018).

More recently, cascaded and multiple-PCM systems have been developed to improve heat transfer and ensure stable temperature profiles. Reddy et al. (2018) reported that cascading multiple PCMs could double or triple the exergy efficiency compared to single PCM systems. Paraffin wax has also gained attention for solar cooking due to its favorable thermal properties (Reddy et al., 2018). Sharma et al. (2021) optimized parabolic solar cookers with sodium acetate-based LHTES, achieving cooking temperatures up to 250 °C. Similarly, Mawire et al. (2010) and Mussard et al. (2013) explored parabolic dish systems with TES, confirming their potential for both boiling and frying applications.

Experimental studies continue to highlight the importance of PCM selection, system integration, and design optimization for solar cooking applications. Rekha et al. (2018) combined palm oil and salt hydrate PCM in a parabolic dish system, achieving a cooking power of 125.3 W with PCM compared to 65.6 W without PCM. Chaudhary et al. (2013) and Saxena et al. (2013) investigated different PCM types for box-type cookers and confirmed the superior performance of systems with PCM-based storage. Overall, TES using PCMs addresses the fundamental limitation of solar cookers—dependence on sunlight availability—while enabling extended, efficient, and indoor cooking capabilities (Fouzi et al., 2017; Selvaraj et al., 2022).

The development of PCM-based solar cooking systems has significantly improved cooking efficiency, extended usability into non-sunshine hours, and expanded the range of cooking applications. Despite challenges such as low PCM conductivity and high material cost, recent advances in cascaded PCMs, indirect heating systems, and hybrid designs demonstrate promising solutions. Continued research is therefore essential for optimizing TES integration in solar cookers, with the ultimate goal of providing affordable, reliable, and sustainable cooking solutions for households worldwide

2.1 Materials (the materials used for construction of the cookers are tabulated in Table 1).

Table 1: Materials, Components and Specifications

COMPONENTS	COOKER A Materials / Specifications	COOKER B Materials / Specifications
<u>Outer box</u>		
Material	MDF wood	MDF wood
Thickness	1.3cm	1.3cm
Dimensions (outer box)	66cm by 56cm	66cm by 56cm
Dimensions (inner)	64cm by 54cm	64cm by 54cm
Dimensions (bottom)	64cm by 54cm	64cm by 54cm
<u>Metal box</u>		
Material	Galvanized iron sheet	Galvanized iron sheet
Thickness	0.5mm	0.5mm
Aperture area	0.345m ²	0.345m ²
Dimensions	64cm by 54cm	64cm by 54cm
Coating	Black	Black
<u>Parabolic reflector</u>		
Type	Plane mirror	Plane mirror
Thickness	4mm	4mm
Dimensions	66cm by 75cm	66cm by 75cm
<u>Glass cover</u>		
Type (inner/outer)	Plain Glass	Plain Glass
Number	2	2
Dimension	66cm by 55cm	65cm by 55cm
Thickness	4mm	4mm
Spacing	3cm	3cm
<u>Plane reflector</u>		
Type	Plane mirror	Plane mirror
Thickness	4mm	4mm
Dimensions	65cm by 55cm	65cm by 55cm
<u>Cooker stand</u>		
Material	Angle iron	Angle iron
Thickness	3mm	3mm
Length	100cm	100cm
<u>Pivoted adjusting bar</u>		
Material	Metal bar	Metal bar
Dimensions	40cm by 2cm	40cm by 2cm
<u>PIPES</u>		
Material	Galvanized pipe	Galvanized pipe
size	1,5cm radius	1,5cm radius
<u>Shea Butter oil Volume</u>	1Litre	
<u>Cow Fat oil Volume</u>		1Liter

2.2. METHODS: Construction of the Double Exposure Solar Cookers

The constructions were done in nine stages:

(i) Construction of Galvanized metal box: The first stage was the construction of a galvanized iron metal box of 64cm length, 54cm breadth and 24 cm width which serves as the main cooker compartment with aperture area of 0.345 m².

(ii) Construction of MDF wooden box that housed the metal box: In the second stage, wooden box made of MDF wood of 66 cm length, 56 cm breadth and 24 cm width was constructed.

(iii) Soldering of Pipes for PCM: Stage three is the construction of a bed of galvanized pipes 30 cm long and radius of 1.5 cm with inlet and outlet which serves as heat storage unit. The pipes contain the phase change material and are attached directly to the bottom of the cooker absorber plate aperture area

(iv) Insulation of metal box with Styrofoam: Stage four 4 is the insulation of the galvanized metal box using Styrofoam to prevent heat losses.

(v) Attachment of the heat storage unit to the metal box: Stage five is the attachment of heat storage unit which was attached directly to the bottom of the aperture area of the galvanized metal box.

(vi) Cooker stand with parabolic reflector attached: Stage 6 is the construction of parabolic mirror reflector that was attached to the cooker stand. This is a galvanized metal sheet that was bent to form the shape of a parabola with strips of plain mirror arranged on it which serves as a parabolic reflector at the bottom of the cooker. The cooker stand was made of angle iron.

(vii) Top and bottom glazing supported by Aluminum frame: In stage seven double plain glasses were used each at both the top and the bottom of the cooker which provides greenhouse effect within the compartment of the cooker. Aluminum frame was used to support the double glazing.

(viii) Upper side mirror booster wooden frame: Stage eight (8) was the construction of the upper side mirror wooden frame. The mirror serves as the reflector while the wooden frame serves as a cover when the cooker is not in use.

(ix) Assembled double exposure solar cooker: The last stage nine (9) was the assembled double exposure solar cooker as shown in plate 1.

Plate 1: The complete assembly of one of the cookers

2.3. Performance Evaluation of the Cookers (Stagnation Test for Cooker A with Shea butter and Cooker B with Cow Fat as PCM).

The two identical cookers integrated with phase change materials (PCMs) were constructed and tested for stagnation temperature test on 23/02/2024 at the testing ground of Sokoto Energy Research Centre, UDUS (13°4' latitude and 5°13' longitude). The two cookers were exposed to solar radiation under similar weather conditions. Cooker A contains one liter of shea butter and Cooker B one liter of cow fat as PCM respectively. Solar radiation data were collected using a CMP3 Pyranometer. Other parameters like wind speed, oven air temperature and ambient temperature during test were also measured at regular intervals of 20 minutes using anemometer and digital thermocouple respectively. The Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) model was used to estimate the first figures of merit using equation (1).

$$F_1 = \frac{TPA_{max} - TA_{av}}{GS_{av}} \quad (1)$$

Where TPA_{MAX} , TA_{av} and GS_{av} are respectively, the maximum absorber plate temperature, the average ambient temperature and the average solar radiation at the time stagnation temperature is reached.

2.4 The Boiling Test (load test)

The boiling tests for the two identical double exposure box type solar cookers were carried out on 24/02/24 using water as load. Two identical blackened aluminium cooking pots of the same size were used. 1000g of water was put in each of the pots and placed in each of the cookers separately at the same time respectively as per IS 1429 (part3)1992. The constant monitoring of water temperature at an interval of 5 minutes with average solar radiation were recorded for both cookers with the help of thermocouples with digital temperature indicator and CMP3 Pyranometer respectively. Ambient temperatures and wind speed were also measured using digital thermometer and anemometer respectively. Adjustment of the reflecting mirrors for each of the cookers was done to direct radiation on top and bottom sides of the cookers using the pivoted adjusting steel bar. The second figure of merit F_2 was determined using equation (2).

$$F_2 = \frac{F_1 (MC)W}{A(t_2 - t_1)} \log_e \frac{[1 - (TW_1 - T_a) / F_1 G_s]}{[1 - (TW_2 - T_a) / F_1 G_s]} \quad (2)$$

Where F_1 and F_2 are first and second figures of merit, MC is mass and specific heat capacity of water, T_{w1} , is the initial water temperature, T_{w2} is the final water temperature, A is the aperture area of the absorber plate, T_a is the ambient temperature and GS is the average solar radiation. $(t_2 - t_1)$ is the time interval (s) during which water temperature rises from T_{w1} to T_{w2} . Buddhi *et al.*, (1999) and (Mullick *et al.*, 2005).

3.0 RESULTS

3.1 Performance of shea butter Cooker (Stagnation Temperature Test Result)

Stagnation temperature test result for shea butter cooker is presented in figure 3.1

Figure 3.1 Stagnation Temperature Test Result for Cooker A with Shea butter as PCM conducted on 23/02/2024.

Results from this figure are used to calculate the first figure of merit using equation (1) and it is found to be 0.15.

3.2 Performance of Cow Fat Cooker (Stagnation Temperature Test Result)

Stagnation temperature test result for cow fat cooker is presented in figure 3.2

Figure 3.2 Stagnation Temperature Test Result for Cooker B with Cow fat as PCM Conducted on 23/02/2024

Results from this figure are used to calculate the first figure of merit using equation (1) and it was found to be 0.16.

3.3 Performance of Shea Butter Cooker (Boiling Test Results)

The boiling test results for shea butter cooker is presented in figure 3.3

Figure 3.3: Water Boiling Test Result for Shea Butter Cooker (SBCBWT) conducted on 24/02/2024
Results from this figure are used to calculate the second figure of merit using equation (2) and it was found to be 0.48 and water in this cooker boiled in 42 minutes.

3.4 Performance of Cow fat Cooker Cooker (Boiling Test Results)

The boiling test results for cow fat cooker is presented in figure 3.3

Figure 4: Water Boiling Test Result for Cow Fat Cooker (CFCBWT) Conducted on 24/02/2024

Results from figure 4 are used to calculate the second figure of merit using equation (2) and is found to be 0.50 and water in this cooker boiled within 39 minutes.

DISCUSSIONS

This study experimentally evaluated shea butter and cow fat as phase change materials (PCMs) in double exposure box-type solar cookers to assess their thermal performance, heat storage behavior, and suitability for off-sunshine cooking. Both stagnation and boiling water tests were performed under identical conditions, enabling a direct comparison of heating rate, heat absorption, phase change, and retention capacity. The stagnation results confirmed that both PCMs significantly enhanced thermal performance. Maximum absorber plate temperatures reached 133 °C for shea butter and 136 °C for cow fat at peak solar radiation of 910 W/m². These values compare favorably with those reported by Chaudhary et al. (2020), who observed 130 °C in a twin-vessel PCM stove, showing that double exposure with PCM integration is competitive.

Shea butter exhibited a latent heat plateau between 50–69 °C, aligning with its melting range, while cow fat plateaued near 56 °C. This behavior reflects reliable latent heat storage capacity. Cow fat's slightly higher peak absorber plate temperature suggests marginally greater thermal conductivity, transferring heat more quickly. Environmental effects also influenced stagnation. The cow fat cooker, tested under fluctuating wind (up to 2.2 m/s), showed small dips in absorber temperature due to convective losses, consistent with findings by El-Sebaï et al. (2005). Nevertheless, both PCMs demonstrated effective solar absorption and storage during stagnation.

Boiling Water Test

Both cookers successfully boiled 1,000 g of water from 29.1 °C to 98.6 °C in under one hour: 42 min for shea butter and 39 min for cow fat. This slight difference reinforces cow fat's faster transfer dynamics. Absorber temperatures during boiling peaked at 130 °C for cow fat and 125 °C for shea butter, while oven air reached 120–125 °C. These values are in line with Sreepathi et al. (2017), who reported oven air temperatures of 125 °C in PCM-assisted box cookers. The observed sequential heat transfer indicated that absorber temperature is higher than oven air and oven air is higher than water temperature and this validated the cooker design. Importantly, the results satisfied BIS water boiling test standards, proving both PCMs effective for practical cooking applications.

Heat Retention and Thermal Storage

The most notable difference emerged in post-sunshine retention. After 7 hours without solar input, water remained at 55.7 °C in the shea butter cooker compared to 42.8 °C in the cow fat cooker. Shea butter therefore demonstrated superior long-term retention due to gradual latent heat release, while cow fat discharged energy more quickly. Sharma et al. (2009) emphasized that PCMs with high latent heat and broad melting ranges prolong heat release, consistent with shea butter's performance. Cow fat, though less effective for extended storage, is suitable where rapid heating is needed.

These results align with Buddhi & Sawhne (1999), who highlighted that PCM effectiveness depends on both melting temperature and discharge profile. Shea butter's broad retention potential makes it ideal for evening cooking, while cow fat resembles the rapid charging PCMs described by Hussein et al. (2008).

In contrast to synthetic PCMs like erythritol or acetamide, which often demand specialized containment and higher cost (Sharma et al., 2005; Yadav, 2013), cow fat and shea butter are affordable, locally available, and non-toxic, making them suitable for rural deployment in regions such as Northern Nigeria. Practically, shea butter is well-suited for late-evening cooking and food warming, while cow fat is advantageous for rapid daytime heating. Their integration into double exposure cookers, which utilize both direct and reflected solar input, enhances overall efficiency and addresses two common challenges in solar cooking: limited cooking hours and poor retention. This makes them promising for sustainable and culturally adaptable cooking in off-grid settings.

Table 2: Summary of the Thermal Performance Test

SN	Type of Cooker	Second Figure of Merit	Maximum Plate Temperature Attained (°C)	Maximum Irradiance (W/m ²)	Wind Speed Range (m/s)	Cooling Water Temperature after 7 hours (°C)
1	Shear butter Cooker with	0.48	133	910	0.2 – 2.1	9 8.5 – 55.7
2	Cow fat Cooker with	0.50	136	910	0.2 – 2.1	9 8.5 – 42.3

CONCLUSION

The comparative evaluation demonstrates that both cow fat and shea butter are viable, low-cost PCMs. Cow fat excels in rapid heating and higher peak performance, while shea butter provides superior long-term retention and sustained discharge. Together, they offer locally sourced, culturally relevant alternatives to commercial PCMs, supporting wider adoption of solar cooking technologies in rural communities.

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NOMENCLATURE

- SBT* = Shea butter temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- CFT* = Cow fat temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- TA* = Ambient temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- TOAA* = Oven air temperature for cooker A without PCM ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- TOAB* = Oven air temperature for cooker B without PCM ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- TPAA* = Absorber plate temperature for Cooker A without PCM ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- TPAB* = Absorber plate temperature for Cooker B without PCM ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- WS* = Wind speed (m/s)
- GS* = Global solar radiation (W/m^2)
- TGA* = Glass temperature of cooker A without PCM ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- TGB* = Glass temperature of cooker B without PCM ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- CFCWBT* = Cow fat cooker boiling water temperature. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- SBCBWT* = Shea butter cooker boiling water temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- TOASB* = Oven air temperature for shea butter cooker ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- TOACF* = Oven air temperature for cow fat cooker ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- MDF* = Medium density fibre
- PCM* = Phase change material
- TES* = Thermal energy storage (joules)
- DEBSC* = Double exposure box type solar cooker
- LHTES* = Latent heat thermal energy storage
- HSMs* = Heat storage materials
- SHS* = Sensible heat storage (joules)
- BTSC* = Box type solar cooker
- Gs* = Global solar radiation (W/m^2)
- WS* = Wind speed (m/s)
- A* = Aperture area (m^2)
- TA* = Ambient temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- F₁* = First figure of merit
- F₂* = Second figure of merit
- T_{w1}* = Initial water temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- T_{w2}* = Final water temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- (Mc)_w* = Product of mass of water and specific heat (J/k)
- (t₂ - t₁)* = Time taken to heat water from *T_{w1}* to *T_{w2}* (seconds)